

Vivek Pathak “Sudarshan” *

Untapping Nature with the Evolution of Poetry

Abstract

This paper is an effort to describe the untapping of Nature through the subtle consciousness of the human mind leading to the creation of Poetry. This effort is derived from the author’s individual experience of realizing the true potential of the natural environment to stimulate the inner core of the Poetic heart. Certain life experiences set a mechanism wherein the search within leads to creativity outside. That is why the author has tried to interpret this motivational flow of inspiration to the human mind through the musings of Nature. Poetry is a way of expression in any language. In the realm of literature, poetry with a rhythm reveals an experience in the minimum words available within the barriers of any language. Over the period, forms of poetry have evolved in different styles that can be exclusively studied by any student of literature. The present paper interprets the impact of Nature on the mind of any poet at various time and at various dimension. Interpreting such an influence of Nature on famous poets from the historical perspective is only a way to vouchsafe the individual experience. This paper is an effort to capture an individual’s experience as a poet and the way an individual mind gets influenced by musings of nature.

Keywords: Poetry, Nature, Rhythm, Consciousness, Inspiration.

Introduction

Poetry writing is a deep process of seeking self-inspiration from Nature. It is a process that may appear simple to the outer world but it is an entangling of the conscious thought flow in tandem with the rhythm of nature. This article blended with individual ideas, intends to establish that Natural environments lead to the motivational thought processes in the Poet’s deep inner core before the evolution of poetry. Poetry itself is an imaginative interpretation of an experience hidden in human subconsciousness that co-relates with the inspiration generated from the rhythmic musings of Nature. Poetry flow from Nature is itself an intricate subject. This flow mutates from Poet’s awareness through emotional response in a chosen language full of understanding, music and rhythm. Poetry in its best form sustains our emotions along with delighting our inner heart. The feeling of joy that we get from poetry is the crux of the stimulation that a poet feels while getting inspired from Nature. Expansion of consciousness from the deeper realms of the vast human mind brings to the core a feeling of elation and mirth.

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Language is only a medium to express the joyous feeling of divinity which a poet gets from the flow of energy through Nature. However vast a subject is Poetry, this article describes untapping of the music of Nature getting translated to the scribblings of the Poet's emotional stimulation.

Literary review

Vachel Lindsay's poem '*The Horrid Voice of Science*', visibly creates an impression of conflict between Poetry and Science. Poetry seems to underpin the aspect of the inherent beauty in existence, whereas Science investigates the current conundrum. As an Engineer who creatively entwines poetry in his profession, the author feels a correlation between the two. Poetry is a way of scholarly communication to express the simplicity in the intricate existence of this Universe.

William Wordsworth, considered the father of English romantic poetry, was a devotee to Nature. His adoration for Nature was noble and rare. Competition with other English poets' wobbles in front of his devotion to Nature. Nature dominated as an influence not only in his poems but in the poems of his contemporary poets and after that also. Robert Frost also got influenced by the concept of Nature. The creative setting of Frost's poetry was in America. This was quite contrary to that of Wordsworth's Nature of Britain. Entwined relation of Nature and Spirituality seems to be an extension of each other. It seems that there is a deep connection of divinity that fills the heart when induced with Natural surroundings. This deep romantic connection definitely inspires a poet to scribble the poetic verses that express the whispers of heart or musings of Nature. Often combined with this feeling for rural life is a generalized romantic melancholy, a sense that change is imminent and that a way of life is being threatened (Johnson, 2015).

The strong influence of Nature in English Romanticism during the contemporary times of Wordsworth and forthwith also depended upon the subject and age of the appearance of the work. Nature appearing as holier and pedantic can be understood from "*let nature be your teacher*"(Van Doren, 1951). Beyond Wordsworth's enjoyable attitude towards Nature, the other English poets too looked to Nature as a primary source of inspiration for their poetry. On the other hand, having influenced with the 'Transcendentalism' movement pioneered by Ralph Waldo Emerson, Frost's attitude towards Nature can be gauged as separately. . Frost's poem "Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening" can vouchsafe for the stated influence. The last

stanza demonstrates the Transcendentalism when Frost mentions about how the woods are lovely, dark and deep, but he adds that he has promises to keep and a long way to go before he sleeps, meaning before he dies, interpreting the connection between life, death and thereafter by Frost is one in the direction of Emerson's school of thought arising from the belief of Transcendentalist movement (Van Doren, 1923).

Indeed, Nature inspires. As was the case with Wordsworth, Nature inspired his poetry. Nature helped soar his imagination. He looked to Nature for knowledge, guidance and information. Whereas, Frost entwined nature towards spirituality. Nature was his meditative vehicle towards Religion and Spirituality. This brings to an understanding that the interpretation of Nature keeps changing with time. It may be a source of generating romanticism from the materialistic world or a blissful attraction to the spiritualistic world. Nature has inspired poets worldwide in different eras and civilizations. Whether the role of Nature has remained as a pedantic pedagogy or inspirational meditation, it has produced results. The influence of Nature has remained the same from times immemorial amongst oriental and occidental creative writers and poets.

Kalidasa was the renowned greatest Indian poet and dramatist of any epoch. His contribution to Sanskrit literature has an elaborate admixture of beauty and divinity in nature. He was a true genius who got inspired by the wonders of Nature with elaborate prayerful gratitude. *Ritusamhara*, *Meghdut*, *Raghuvansham* and *Kumarsambhavam* were creatively written by Kalidasa in Sanskrit. These writings were eulogies to Nature in his own creative style and mature depiction. In some of the creations there were eco-critical references to Nature. "Kalidas's works preserves for us moments of beauty, incidents of courage, art of sacrifice and fleeting moods of the human heart." (Radhakrishnan, 1977)

In the evolved materialistic world eco-criticism inspired from Nature can influence the growth of society. This exemplifies the utility of creativity derived from the influence of Nature. "*If mortals dwell in that they save the earth and if poetry is the original admission of dwelling, the poetry is the place where we save the earth.*" (Bate, 2002) For bringing a blissful state to this world, it is very important to love nature and play to its rules under its inspiration. In this state of existence, the creative mind of a poet can contribute to the growth of humanity and society.

Nature inspires a poetic mind. The predicament in life under the wanton effects of materialism induces the sanctum sanctorum of humanity by virtue of creativity influenced by Nature.

Mathew Arnold in his Literary criticism “The study of Poetry” draws attention to his concern about “high destiny” of the poetry. He believes that “mankind will discover that we have to turn to poetry to interpret life for us, to console us, to sustain us”. For Arnold, emotions and earnestness are also tantamount to the seriousness of the subject. “The superior character of truth and seriousness, in the matter and substance of the best poetry is inseparable from the superiority diction and movement marking its style and manner.” Arnold believes that poetry should both uplift and console.

“The future of poetry is immense, because in poetry, where it is worthy of its high destinies, our race, as time goes on, will find an ever surer and surer stay. There is not a creed which is not shaken, not an accredited dogma which is not shown to be questionable, not a received tradition which does not threaten to dissolve. Our religion has materialised itself in the fact, in the supposed fact; it has attached its emotion to the fact, and now the fact is failing it. But for poetry the idea is everything; the rest is a world of illusion, of divine illusion. Poetry attaches its emotion to the idea; the idea is the fact. The strongest part of our religion to-day is its unconscious poetry.”(Arnold, 1880)

Criticism in different dimensions may vary but the poet’s character predominates the poetic expression. The lofty words flowing out of his consciousness are amalgamated with the level of personal experiences in the world and the individual interpretation of the experience. Studying about various expressions in different styles of poets is itself a vast and deep area of introspection. Differences lay in expression yet there remains always a common thread of unity among the different poets. Influence of Nature, the flow of thoughts, reassembling thoughts in order, retaining the creative emotions, deleting the unwanted words, perspective of experience and decoding a common thread of divinity lead to creative expression of any poetry.

Findings

This analysis identifies the connectivity of ideological stimulus by Nature in any poetic mind. In this context, ‘Nature’ is referred to any place or action that leads to this motivation. The happening may be of any type, positive or negative, but it leads to creative stimulation. Sometimes it remains a beautiful experience under the inspiration when poetry is created in a flow. At times, poets do wonder as to how this was written or created. Truly, there remains an inspiration from the divine. One may wonder about variegated hues embedded in creative

writings. The hues are on the canvas of creative work through an inspiration that flows naturally from the Universe.

The mind is only a machine through which this inspiration flows. Thoughts get embedded in the storage of individual human consciousness and thereby produced in the world as a creative output. Individual experience corroborates that ideas flow to mind after witnessing any activity from the outside world. Then there may remain a period of lull which may extend up to a period of hours to days or months or years. Then someday sometime somewhere, the poet starts writing his or her views in the grammatical syntax or the individual learning the poet has received in the individual grooming over the years. When it is referred to hues, these hues are due to individual seasoning in the conscious creation of the universe. Creativity is the positive flow of energy in the universe. It may take any form. Creativity suppressed over a period gets convoluted as a negative expression. This negative expression of energy may prove destructive to the society.

Blended in the world of poetry is 'Romanticism'. Imagination used in Keats's '*Ode to a Nightingale*' and Shelly's '*Skylark*' depicts their respective individual experiences during their times. Application of fantasy and depicting romanticism drawn through Nature provided a dominating aura to the coming generation of poetic students. Romanticism was always a subject of interest to the critics and scholars of the literature. These poets ameliorated the feeling of joy by disposing of the agony by setting perspective beauty drawn from Nature. Nature has many hidden answers to the cacophony of confused semantics of the human mind. Creativity by the human mind brings out the flow of energy in the realm of consciousness. A flowing river is always perfect in its struggle and sound of continuous flowing water. Every layer of water changes every moment. Nature is always a constant evolution. This change gets reflected in the poetic creativity of the poet. That is the magic of creativity because it is a flowing energy. Energy is continually getting transformed from one form to another. Energy is neither created nor destroyed. Only change is observed in its representation. The flow of water in the river is an example of freshness with continuously evolving positive transformation. To the contrary, the stagnated water of the pond is an example of staleness with the deadly infusion of harmful destruction.

Birth and death remain the truth of this Universe of Life. Life remains ever evolving and constantly growing with a flow. In this eternal life, birth and death are two phases. Our relative experiences gathered amidst the various charismatic and melancholy phases of life direct us

towards appropriate connections in this world. Life is a common thread in Nature of the Universe. Hence, there is a common thread in all the poetic expressions. That common thread is Nature or Divinity. Poets go astray while moving deeper into the consciousness. Yet this dream like experience remains a hidden thought in their subconscious mind. When any stimulation from Nature happens, the churning of the poetic mind happens. In that process the entwined thoughts appear in the form of poetry. Creativity is an expression of divine flow and divinity is naturally present in the universe.

Many instances were observed in the digressing behaviour of poets. This aberration was observed due to the mishandling of their respective perceived sentiments. It may be misconstrued behaviour generated from sentiments induced mind. Yet during various timelines their respective social activities like drinking, smoking, promiscuity, continued. These are examples of immature handling of energy flow through the individual consciousness. At times, the ideas remain the same but expressions differ. Individuals may find the expression through poetry either too focussed in interpretation or digressive beyond understanding. Poets at times digress from thinking about the problem and revert to it at a later stage. During this 'Gap' between time and dimension, creativity gets fostered as a 'Poetry'. This poetry leads to either problem projection or solution soliciting. This so-called 'Gap' is a time when the mind works to generate creativity after seeking inspiration from Nature. Poetry is truly more effective in creating dialogues among the intellectual class and sundry public.

Reflection

Some Literature students gravitate naturally towards poetry, seeing depth in the verses generating a meaningful interpreted expression. Some consider them as a flawed dramatic geriatric expression of scapegoats. To the beginners dawning the world of poetry, it gets revealed as four types: Free verse (a poem without defined rhyme), Haiku (a Japanese origin poem which contains three lines with five, seven and five syllables, respectively), Limerick (a humorous poem of five lines using a rhythmic scheme of abba) and Sonnet (a fourteen-line rhyming poem, typically consisting of ten syllables each line).

While interpreting the composed poem "Tears" as follows:

*A crying bird,
Perched,*

*On the branch,
 Of a tree,
 At the river bank,
 Thought,
 My tears are small, tiny ones,
 While, whose tears are you,
 O Flowing one.*

Through this expression of a crying bird in tears, an outflow of thought is being made to relate to the flowing river. A question is raised by a living bird who represents the life of a being. Whereas, the river represents the vast Nature that at times is beyond the realm of an interpretation. That is why the question is raised – *If my tears are small, tiny ones; while, whose tears are you, O flowing one?* Here, there is the flow of two things – the flow of tears in a bird who is sitting on the branch of a tree. There is another flow of water in the river on whose bank the tree is standing. It is the query raised to the super consciousness by an individual consciousness. The answer remains mystified on a search. Hence, the poem rests in a question. Furthermore, another one titled “Patience”:

*O Ocean!
 Your gurgle there,
 With a roar,
 Amidst you,
 Lies an oyster,
 Calm and serene,
 Waiting for a raindrop,
 To come.*

It is through the observation made by the poet while observing the ocean and oyster. If ocean is gurgling in noise, its whole being must be struggling. Yet deep inside the depth of the ocean lies an oyster – waiting in patience *for a rain drop to come*. So that oyster converts this raindrop into a pearl in a complete silence. Now this silence is inside the depth of the ocean which is gurgling at the surface with a roaring noise. In the centre of an atom there is a nucleus. The nucleus is a power centre, yet it is calm. The electrons moving around the nucleus remain

constantly in movement. If a movement is noise, then a silence is powerful. In the struggling conscience of the human being, there is a silence. A silence that always remains a continually uninterpreted and misinterpreted mystery. Now, this silence has its language. There is a definite differentiation between the silence of a temple, the silence of the church, the silence of a graveyard, the silence of a forest, the silence after a riot and the silence of meditation.

Let these lines titled “Cheat” be interpreted as:

*A stick tells the tottering man,
You rely on me,
When the world betrays you,
But the old man asks,
Of what use are you to me?*

With this question from an inanimate object for an animate object, there is a message pointing to the selfish nature of a human being. This selfish worldly nature of any human being makes him run wantonly after worldly objects, use them to his or her selfish purpose and then discard them. This is a fact about any worldly-minded person. During trouble they do rely on the selfless helpful people but when their work is finished, they forget their generosity. At times they refuse to accept their grand generosity. The act which is described as indicative when *the old man asks, of what use are you to me*. This queer question is a blatant denial of the worldly-minded person to a selfless spiritual person (denoted by a stick). Sticks do not raise questions. Yet person with a spiritual bent of mind become selfless and humble after a prolonged period of spiritual exercises. Though such people may not ask questions, yet to give it a poetic turn such a question is asked by user to the object. The reply comes readily in its natural form.

Now interpreting this translated poem from Hindi titled “Dream”:

*Having seen you in a dream,
Some work was achieved;
When awoke from dream,
Night had slowly vanished.*

When you came in the dream,

*Some relationship was formed;
In the broken dreams,
Nearly that was doomed.*

*Whole life has gone thinking of you,
Conundrum has kept building;
I kept on weaving dreams,
The whole caravan kept passing.*

In a dream, someone is seen. That someone is from the divine world. When sleep was broken, the dream vanished in its existence. The memory of that dream remained afresh in the mind and heart of the poet. Then there is an interpretation that *when you came in the dream, a special relationship was formed*, but that relationship was doomed when the dream was broken. With memories intact afresh of that dream, my whole life has passed away thinking of you. Since that someone is not seen for long, a quest remains. Whether that dream was a delusion or a fact. Life passes by in the dreamland called the world with memories of the dream. Nevertheless, the caravan of activities kept passing by in life and we remain living in our respective worlds. There is always a search of divinity within the sub-conscious mind. That search is quite deep within the human consciousness. In the realm of human consciousness, are encountered dreams too. In this poem, the dream is referred by the outside world that is itself an illusory dream. We feel like living then someday we slowly pass away. When a person is born, that person will die. In between death and birth, this life's journey is referred to as a caravan passing by.

Another poem titled "Rainbow" is expressed as:

*Birds fly,
High in the sky,
To watch,
The rainbow,
Beyond the raindrops,
Indeed, blessed is the bee,
Who while sitting,
Watches the rainbow,
Beyond the dewdrop,*

On the petal rose.

This poem describes the quest of two persons of two different attitudes and approaches in different dimensions. These two persons with different natures are trying their respective path of God realization. One who is struggling is indicated as a bird. Bird is described as a Jnana yogi, a knowledge seeker. He struggles and makes efforts, runs around, travels a lot. Then sees the rainbow(God) high in the sky(lofty thoughts) after years of practice. The other one is denoted as a Bee, a bhakta yogi, an emotional poetic seeker. He struggles in deep prayer and silence. He dedicates himself to singing and devotion. He sees the rainbow(God) on the rose petal(heart). The important point is that the both seek God through the different type of efforts.

Another poem revealed after observing the Taj Mahal is expressed as:

*What is there in a heart like Shah Jehan,
That constructs only a mausoleum;
Praiseworthy it would be for Emperor,
Had he created history in Love.*

*History is also silent on this,
That in one monument of Love;
Many unknown hands were sacrificed,
Not a single tomb exists in their memory.*

*This is an actual fact of life, O Friend!
That Love has always brought blood shed;
Had there been talks for Love,
Then why the world is like this.*

This poem is another perspective to peep into a different perspective of beauty. Beauty in Nature can have the ingrained ugliness of the creation. Peacock dances and brings rhythm to the dance of existence. It seems so perfectly attuned to the beauty of Nature. This beauty vanishes when a peacock eats a snake to survive. Similarly, how beautiful the blooming of Lotus is? Nevertheless, the place where it blooms that water generates a stench. From this poem it is interpreted that if the Taj Mahal is beautiful, then the barbarous act of the Emperor to

amputate the hands of workers was the most terrible. The story of this act may be doubtful but history has ample pieces of evidence to substantiate such an action. Even if the hands were not amputated, there is still a story of hardships faced by toiling human workers. The poem questions why history is silent on fact. Why is it glorifying eulogies for the action of an emperor who wasted so much money to create a mausoleum in memory of his beloved queen? From the perspective of development, such an art is questionable. It is only a tomb. The creation of a Tomb is alien to Hindu practice. It is a practice of foreign land. It is indeed a known fact that the Mughals were from outside the country, so was the practice. With this perspective, the poem raises a question as to why the history of love is written in blood. If there is love indeed, then why the bloodshed? Love and violence are contrary to each other. War cannot bring peace. If peace is not there, then love cannot prosper. Historical perspectives are shrouded in such mysteries that seem contrary to each other. It is the same as understanding the facts of beauty behind the existence of a peacock.

I search for peace

The divine one

While O'Breeze

You whisper in the leaves

The silence is here

The peaceful one

I search for the truth

The holy one

While O'Oyester

You lay silent

In the sea

With the transformation

The truthful one

We all tread a journey of the spiritual world, seeking peace in the depth of silence. This poem interprets the peace of silence from the whisper in leaves by the breeze. This poem also observes the transcendental silence in the patience of the oyster in the depth of the trembling sea. Peace exists in such turbulence of activity. The centre of the cell or atom is the most silent yet powerful supreme zone. In the depth of Tornado, silence exists. Silence has its power, its language. Only humans need to interpret the language of silence. The same can be perceived

in silence of the graveyard, the meditation hall, the deep prayer, the garden of flowers and the depth of meditation.

*Leaf fell from the tree
But it never asked
Why have you left me?
Then
Why do you seek O' Earth
The question
Is it a burden on you?*

From the standpoint of writing, this poem seems to present a confused narrative and a delusive interpretation. Nevertheless, it can be understood if the thread of silence is to be deciphered for the hidden meaning. This poem is a silent communication between earth and tree. In one sense, the material and the spiritual interpretation of the people on earth. A leaf falls from the tree, but the tree never gets possessive about the right of a leaf falling from the tree. Tree never raises questions of bringing up the leaf and nurturing it for years. It accepts the neutrality of detachment which may happen at any time of any lively object. Now, the query is raised to the Earth. Is the falling of leaf a burden to the Earth? It is a metaphorical way of asking that why this world interprets joining of a well-groomed individual into the flurry of its activities as a burden? If the old fades away, then the new makes a space. That is the way Nature has worked from time immemorial. Why an older person who has given years of his youthful energy for this world becomes redundant someday marked as unacceptable? Is old age a signal for dread? Why are the questions being raised even in families and societies? If old is gold, then old must be cherished as a newly born child. If the wails of a child give a good memory, then the pang of the old age must be respected in a timely respectful mannerism. That is the wonder of life as it goes on.

Analysis

The ideas are creatively born in the mind of a poet in the deep silence of consciousness. The din of hidden experiences of sub-consciousness blend the poetry as a multi-coloured painting on the canvas of this universe. It is true that Nature stimulates the poetic mind but that stimulus remains quite individual. Individual interpretation from the respective experience creates a

poetic creation that seems different. Citing famous poets like Frost, Wordsworth and Kalidasa who were born and lived in different dimensions of time and place, brings forth the one thin common thread – Inspiration.

Inspiration has remained universal. Inspiration is generated beyond any dimension defined by consciousness. Psychological interpretation of any incident may differ, but the inspirational source remains the same. Inspiration flows from Nature to individual consciousness, wherein creativity transforms into a full format. As a poetic mind, this can be vouchsafed through individual observations. Poetry is a type of format for expressing an idea in minimum words with rhythm attached. The same creativity can also be transformed into any other format of creative writing. Type of creative writing is not the subject of discussion here. Therefore, my ideas are directed specifically to the influence of Nature on any poetic mind. Ample pieces of evidence exist in the literature of various languages to substantiate this claim. Creativity is beyond the precincts of time and place. It has a common thread generated by Inspiration. The source of inspiration may vary, but it is ultimately associated with Universe in one form or another.

Interpretation from Nature remains divergent and multifaceted, yet there is one single strand where all interpretations and argument vanish into silence. This silence is the power behind every gargantuan transformation we see around us. Transformation seems disturbing because it re-aligns the order, but in the din of transformation lay calmness of silence. Poets interpret that silence which whispers in their hearts. Heart brings creativity through intellectual stimulation. Sentiments get expressed through words. Then words get interpreted by individual consciousness. So, the interpretations get varied too. What remains constant is the silence amidst the variety of activities. Poets see that silence through their inner eye and create a documented version of their conscious interpretation.

Conclusion

Since immemorial times, poets have demonstrated the expression of creativity, which has borne chiefly from the influence of Nature. Universe through Natural ways influences the mind of a poet. An inspired poetic mind expresses emotions in the format of creative writing. Inspiration from Nature motivates the writing of a poet. The flow of thoughts from the mind of the poet creates a rhythm in expressions. An incident from Nature leads the poetic mind to interpret that incident. The poetic mind blends that interpretation with the individual experience and

expresses it in the form of creative output. What we see outside in the world in the form of poetry is really an inspiration of an individual consciousness penned down in words in rhythm or otherwise. How the mind churns the thought process? Processing of these verses in the mind can be understood by the indicative factors. These indicative factors are captured well in this paper. Findings here in this article are based upon an individual experience. Hence the same can be disputed by any other person with his or her different way of processing. Whatever may be a reason for the dispute, the typical derivation, regarding the inspiration of the human mind from Nature, remains the same. Understanding and Interpretation depend upon the rational standpoint of the reader. Though Poetic communication has remained an exciting subject worldwide, actual experience can never be surmised through words.

Notes

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